

CO-OPERAS workshop, Brussels, March 03 2019

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Chair: Elena Giglia

The CO-OPERAS workshop in Brussels on March 3rd was the conclusion of a series initiated in Porto at the FAIR Open Science event. Based on the reports of the previous workshops and the recently published report from ALLEA, the participants came out with some strong propositions and analysis on Social Sciences and Humanities outputs FAIRification.

SSH FAIRification strategies

Survival of the Humanities is at stake if we don't find a balance between preserving the specificity of the field and adapting/adopting the standards necessary to integrate them into the EOSC (e.g. through the SSHOC project).

FAIR data can foster cooperation outside Humanities with other disciplines (aspect that is relevant also in the prospect of the life-or-death context mentioned above).

There is still no consensus on what "data" is in our field (many definitions are too generic, see ALLEA's report).

To define data you need to consider the process of data production, going as deep as possible in research practices. The definition should be linked to the workflow of knowledge creation. The concrete digital context (open public depositories, servers, etc.) has also to have its place in the definition.

A focus on digital/analogical similarities and divergences can help to solve the aporia of a the data processing.

It would be useful to reflect on the relationship between Humanities and Social sciences: are the data the same? It depends on the research objects and methods; there are however overlaps in some cases and the data corresponding to each field is impossible to split.

Researchers' engagement

A cultural shift is needed: from "I publish a paper and I'm done" to "I take care of anything I used to write my paper". It relates also with the challenge of data preservation after the end of the project.

Research assessment is creating a vicious circle: try to make it virtuous (change the criteria but also change the habits).

Focus on the WHY and HOW (why sharing data? why ensuring its interoperability, preservation?) and create narratives on it.

OPERAS infrastructure should be research driven, as it is useless to build an infrastructure not respondent to the researchers' needs and then ask "why researchers don't use it? How to engage them?" - we already have many examples of this kind.

FAIR tools and training

Questions on data management, tools, licences, sharing ought to be addressed during the Design phase of the research, in a responsible way as we are dealing with public money.

Extreme need of a Humanities data repository (e.g. French repository [Nakala](#)) that is easy to use.

Offer an easy-to-use environment in which researchers do Open Science in a seamless, "transparent" way without even acknowledge it ([COARC-SPARC principles](#)).

Measure the impact/use of the infrastructure.

Extreme need for a registry of tool – there is a lot of existing tools we simply don't know about.

If we don't provide suitable and sustainable tools soon, researchers will use what the market offers (no FAIR guarantee).

FAIR training and skills are needed.

Sustainability of services and tools is crucial, as it is pointless to use a tool disappearing after 2 years.

A single point of access to publications with a good filtering system is crucial (TRIPLE project is currently building one).

Interoperability

Metadata are essential. We could easily build a "[Time machine](#)" in every discipline, and all together, via metadata using the already existing data and opening them as Linked Open Data.

Organize collaborative work on vocabularies and ontologies.

Organize Hackathons/ Metadata4machines workshops.

Proposition of actions

- invite successful projects/infrastructures to share their best practices
- invite projects/research groups and help them make their data FAIR and/or their services COAR-SPARC compatible
- workshops on vocabularies and ontologies
- disciplinary workshops on how the data is produced
- build a registry of tools (in collaboration with DARIAH, SSHOC)
- Create a new *data journal* devoted to discussing SSH data: to increase interest for FAIR data in SSH and give publicity to projects that try to produce and publish FAIR data